

CUBIC IDEALS OF Γ - SEMIGROUPS

V. Chinnadurai* & K. Bharathivelan**

* Associate Professor, Department of Mathematics, Annamalai University, Chidambaram, Tamilnadu

** Department of Mathematics, Annamalai University, Chidambaram, Tamilnadu

Abstract:

In this paper, we defined new notion of cubic ideals of Γ -semigroups, which is generalized concept of fuzzy ideals of Γ -semigroups. We also investigated some of its properties with examples.

Index Terms - Semigroup, Γ -Semigroup, Regular Γ -Semigroup, Ideal, Bi-Ideal, Interior Ideal, Cubic Ideal, Cubic Bi-Ideal & Cubic Interior Ideal

1. Introduction:

Zadeh [16] initiated the concept of fuzzy sets in 1965. In 1975, Zadeh [17] made an extension concept of a fuzzy set by an interval-valued fuzzy set. A semigroup is an algebraic structure consisting of a non-empty sets together with an associative binary operation. The formal study of semigroups began in the early 20th century. In 1981 Sen [14] introduced the notion of Γ -semigroup as a generalization of semigroup and ternary semigroup. Many results of semigroups could be extended to Γ -semigroups directly and via operator semigroups of a Γ -semigroups. Many authors have studied semigroups in terms of fuzzy sets. Kuroki [10] is the main contributor of this study. Motivated by Kuroki [10] Sardar et al. [13] have initiated the study of Γ -semigroups in terms of fuzzy sets. Kuroki [10] introduced the notion of fuzzy ideals and fuzzy bi-ideals in semigroups. Atanassov [1] introduced intuitionistic fuzzy set is characterized by a membership function and a non-membership function for each element in the Universe. In 2010, K. Hur and H.W. Kang [4] introduced interval-valued fuzzy subgroups and rings. Jun et al. [7] introduced the new concept called cubic sets. These structures encompass interval-valued fuzzy set and fuzzy set. Also Jun et al. [6] introduced the notion of cubic subgroups. Vijayabalaji et al. [15] introduced the notion of cubic linear space. V. Chinnadurai et al. [3] introduced cubic ring. The purpose of this paper to introduce the notion of cubic ideals of Γ -semigroups and we provide some results on it.

2. Introduction:

Now we recall some known concepts related to cubic ideals of Γ - semigroups from the literature, which will be needed in the sequel.

Definition 2.1: [12] Let S be a semigroup. By a subsemigroup of S , we mean a non-empty subset A of S such that $A^2 \subseteq A$.

Definition 2.2: [12] A non-empty subset A of a Γ - semigroup S is said to be a Γ -subsemigroup of S if $A\Gamma A \subseteq A$.

Definition 2.3: [2] A non-empty subset A of a Γ - semigroup S is called left (right) ideal of S such that $S\Gamma A \subseteq A$ ($A\Gamma S \subseteq A$). If A is both a left and a right ideal of a Γ - semigroup S , then we say A is an ideal of S .

Definition 2.4: [2] A Γ -subsemigroup A of a Γ - semigroup S is called a bi-ideal of S if $A\Gamma S\Gamma A \subseteq A$.

Definition 2.5: [2] A Γ -subsemigroup A of a Γ - semigroup S is called an interior ideal of S if $S\Gamma A\Gamma S \subseteq A$.

Definition 2.6: [12] Let S be a Γ - semigroup and S_1 be a Γ_1 - semigroup. A pair of mappings $f_1: S \rightarrow S_1$ and $f_2: \Gamma \rightarrow \Gamma_1$ is said to be a homomorphism from (S, Γ) to (S_1, Γ_1) , if $f_1(x\gamma y) = f_1(x) f_2(\gamma) f_1(y) \quad \forall x, y \in S \text{ and } \forall \gamma \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.7: [2] Let X be a non-empty set. A mapping $\bar{\mu}: X \rightarrow D[0,1]$ is called interval-valued fuzzy set, where $D[0,1]$ denote the family of all closed sub intervals of $[0, 1]$ and a mapping $\lambda: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ is a fuzzy set in X .

Definition 2.8: [2] A fuzzy subset μ of X is called a fuzzy left (right) ideal of X , if $\mu(xy) \geq \mu(y)$, $(\mu(xy) \geq \mu(x)) \quad \forall x, y \in X$.

if μ is both a fuzzy left and a fuzzy right ideal of X , then μ is called a fuzzy ideal of X .

Definition 2.9: [2] An interval-valued fuzzy subset $\bar{\mu}$ of X is called a interval-valued fuzzy left (right) ideal of X , if $\bar{\mu}(xy) \geq \bar{\mu}(y)$, $(\bar{\mu}(xy) \geq \bar{\mu}(x)), \forall x, y \in X$. If $\bar{\mu}$ is both an i-v fuzzy left and i-v fuzzy right ideal of X , then $\bar{\mu}$ is called an i-v fuzzy ideal of X .

Definition 2.10: [2] A fuzzy subset μ of X is called a fuzzy bi-ideal of X , if

i) $\mu(xy) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$
 ii) $\mu(xyz) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(z)\}, \forall x, y, z \in X$

Definition 2.11: [2] A fuzzy subset μ of X is called a fuzzy interior ideal of X , if

i) $\mu(xy) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$
 ii) $\mu(xyz) \geq \mu(y) \quad \forall x, y, z \in X$.

Definition 2.12: [2] A fuzzy subset μ of a Γ - semigroup S is called a fuzzy Γ -subsemigroup of S , if $\mu(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}. \quad \forall x, y \in S \text{ and } \forall \gamma \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.13: [7] Let X be a non empty set. A cubic set \mathcal{A} in X is a structure of the form $\mathcal{A} = \{ \langle x, \bar{\mu}_A(x), \lambda(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ and denoted by $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}_A, \lambda \rangle$, where $\bar{\mu}_A = [\mu_A^-, \mu_A^+]$ is an interval-valued fuzzy set (briefly, IVF) in X and λ is a fuzzy set in X .

Definition 2.14: [7] The complement of $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}_A, \lambda \rangle$ is defined by $\mathcal{A}^c = \{ \langle x, (\bar{\mu}_A)^c(x), 1 - \lambda(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$.

Definition 2.15: [7] For any $\mathcal{A}_i = \{ \langle x, \bar{\mu}_i(x), \lambda_i(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$ where $i \in \Lambda$ (index set), we have the following,

- i) $\cap_{R, i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i = \{ \langle x, (\cap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i)(x), (\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \lambda_i)(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$
(R - intersection)
- ii) $\cup_{R, i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i = \{ \langle x, (\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i)(x), (\cap_{i \in \Lambda} \lambda_i)(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$
(R - union)
- iii) $\cap_{P, i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i = \{ \langle x, (\cap_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i)(x), (\cap_{i \in \Lambda} \lambda_i)(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$
(P - intersection)
- iv) $\cup_{P, i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i = \{ \langle x, (\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \bar{\mu}_i)(x), (\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \lambda_i)(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$
(P - union)

Definition 2.16: [13] Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \lambda \rangle$ is a cubic set in X , then $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \lambda \rangle$ is a cubic KU-ideal of X if and only if for all $\tilde{t} \in D[0,1]$ and $s \in [0,1]$, the set $U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, s)$ is either empty or a KU-ideal of X .

Definition 2.17: [8] For any non-empty subset G of a set X , the characteristic cubic set of G is defined to be a structure $\chi_G(x) = \langle x, \bar{\mu}_{\chi_G}(x), \gamma_{\chi_G}(x) : x \in X \rangle$ which is briefly denoted by $\chi_G(x) = \langle \bar{\mu}_{\chi_G}(x), \gamma_{\chi_G}(x) \rangle$.

$$\text{Where } \bar{\mu}_{\chi_G}(x) = \begin{cases} [1,1] & \text{if } x \in G \\ [0,0] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \text{ and } \gamma_{\chi_G}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \in G \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

3. Main Results:

In this section, we introduced the notion of cubic ideals of Γ -semigroups and discuss some of its properties. Throughout this paper S stands for Γ - semigroup unless otherwise specified.

Definition 3.1: A non-empty cubic subset $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ of S is called a cubic left (right) ideal of S , if it satisfies

- i) $\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \bar{\mu}(y), (\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \bar{\mu}(x))$
- ii) $\omega(x\gamma y) \leq \omega(y), (\omega(x\gamma y) \leq \omega(x)) \quad \forall x, y \in S \text{ and } \forall \gamma \in \Gamma$.

A non-empty cubic subset $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ of S is called a cubic ideal of S , if it is a cubic left ideal and a cubic right ideal of S .

Definition 3.2: A non-empty cubic subset $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ of S is called a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of S , if it satisfies

i) $\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\}$,

ii) $\omega(x\gamma y) \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\}$, $\forall x, y \in S$ and $\forall \gamma \in \Gamma$.

Definition 3.3: A cubic Γ -subsemigroup $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ of S is called a cubic bi-ideal of S , if it satisfies

i) $\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(z)\}$

ii) $\omega(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(z)\} \forall x, y, z \in S$ and $\forall \alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Example 3.4: Let $S = \{0, a, b, c\}$ and $\Gamma = \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma\}$ be the non-empty set of binary operations defined below:

γ	0	a	b	c
0	0	0	0	0
a	0	a	0	a
b	0	b	0	c
c	0	0	0	b

α	0	a	b	c
0	0	0	0	0
a	a	a	a	a
b	0	0	0	b
c	0	0	0	c

β	0	a	b	c
0	0	0	0	0
a	0	a	0	0
b	0	0	b	0
c	0	0	0	c

Clearly S is a Γ - semigroup. Moreover,

Define an interval-valued fuzzy set $\bar{\mu}:S \rightarrow D[0,1]$ by,

$\bar{\mu}(0)=[0.8,0.9]$, $\bar{\mu}(a)=[0.5,0.6]$, $\bar{\mu}(b)=[0.3,0.4]$ and $\bar{\mu}(c)=[0.1,0.2]$ is an interval-valued fuzzy bi-ideal of S .

Define a fuzzy set $\omega:S \rightarrow [0,1]$ by, $\omega(0)=0.2$, $\omega(a)=0.4$, $\omega(b)=0.6$ and $\omega(c)=0.8$ is a fuzzy bi-ideal of S .

Hence $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of Γ -semigroup S .

Definition 3.5: A cubic Γ -subsemigroup $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ of S is called a cubic interior ideal of S , if it satisfies

i) $\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \bar{\mu}(y)$,

ii) $\omega(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \omega(y)$, $\forall x, y, z \in S$ and $\forall \alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Example 3.6: Let $S = \{0, a, b, c\}$ and $\Gamma = \{\alpha, \beta, \gamma\}$ be the non-empty set of binary operations defined below:

γ	0	a	b	c
0	0	0	0	0
a	0	a	0	a
b	0	b	0	c
c	0	0	0	b

α	0	a	b	c
0	0	0	0	0
a	a	a	a	a
b	0	0	0	b
c	0	0	0	c

β	0	a	b	c
0	0	0	0	0
a	0	a	0	0
b	0	0	b	0
c	0	0	0	c

Clearly S is a Γ - semigroup. Moreover,

Define an interval-valued fuzzy set $\bar{\mu}:S \rightarrow D[0,1]$ by,

$\bar{\mu}(0)=[0.9,1]$, $\bar{\mu}(a)=[0.7,0.8]$, $\bar{\mu}(b)=[0.5,0.6]$ and $\bar{\mu}(c)=[0.3,0.4]$ is an interval-valued fuzzy interior ideal of S .

And define an fuzzy set $\omega:S \rightarrow [0,1]$ by, $\omega(0)=0$, $\omega(a)=0.5$, $\omega(b)=0.8$ and $\omega(c)=1$ is a fuzzy interior ideal of S .

Hence $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of Γ - semigroup S .

Definition 3.7: Let $\mathcal{A}_1 = \langle \bar{\mu}_1, \gamma_1 \rangle$ and $\mathcal{A}_2 = \langle \bar{\mu}_2, \gamma_2 \rangle$ be any two cubic sets of S then the following cubic sets of S are defined as follows,

$$(\mathcal{A}_1 \odot \mathcal{A}_2)(x) = \begin{cases} (\bar{\mu}_1 \tilde{\circ} \bar{\mu}_2)(x) = \begin{cases} \min\{\bar{\mu}(p), \bar{\mu}(q)\} & \text{for all } p, q \in S, \gamma \in \Gamma \\ [0,0] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ (\omega_1 \circ \omega_2)(x) = \begin{cases} \max\{\omega(p), \omega(q)\} & \text{for all } p, q \in S, \gamma \in \Gamma \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{cases}$$

$$(\mathcal{A}_1 \otimes \mathcal{A}_2)(x) = \begin{cases} (\bar{\mu}_1 \tilde{*} \bar{\mu}_2)(x) = \begin{cases} \min\{\bar{\mu}_1(a), \bar{\mu}_2(b)\} & \forall a, b \in S, \gamma \in \Gamma \\ [0,0] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ (\gamma_1 * \gamma_2)(x) = \begin{cases} \max\{\gamma_1(a), \gamma_2(b)\} & \forall a, b \in S, \gamma \in \Gamma \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{cases}$$

Definition 3.8: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic interior ideal of S . Define $U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n) = \{x \in S \mid \bar{\mu}(x) \geq \tilde{t} \text{ and } \omega(x) \leq n\}$, where $\tilde{t} \in D[0,1]$ and $n \in [0,1]$ is called the level set of \mathcal{A} .

Theorem 3.9: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic ideal of S . If S is an intra regular, then $\mathcal{A}(a) = \mathcal{A}(a\beta a)$ for all $a \in S, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Proof: Let a be any element of S . Since S is intra regular then there exist $x, y \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \Gamma$.

Such that $a = x\alpha a\beta a\gamma y$, then $\bar{\mu}(a) = \bar{\mu}(x\alpha a\beta a\gamma y) \geq \bar{\mu}(x\alpha a\beta a) \geq \bar{\mu}(a\beta a) \geq \bar{\mu}(a)$ and $\omega(a) = \omega(x\alpha a\beta a\gamma y) \leq \omega(x\alpha a\beta a) \leq \omega(a\beta a) \leq \omega(a)$

Thus $\bar{\mu}(a) = \bar{\mu}(a\beta a)$ and $\omega(a) = \omega(a\beta a)$.

Hence $\mathcal{A}(a) = \mathcal{A}(a\beta a)$.

Theorem 3.10: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic ideal of S . If S is an intra regular, then $\mathcal{A}(a\beta b) = \mathcal{A}(b\beta a)$ for all $a \in S, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Proof: Let $a, b \in S$ and $\beta \in \Gamma$. By the above theorem, we have

$$\bar{\mu}(a\beta b) = \bar{\mu}(a\beta b\beta a\beta b) \geq \bar{\mu}(a\beta(b\beta a)\beta b) \geq \bar{\mu}(b\beta a)$$

$$\bar{\mu}(b\beta a) = \bar{\mu}(b\beta a\beta b\beta a) \geq \bar{\mu}(b\beta(a\beta b)\beta a) \geq \bar{\mu}(a\beta b) \text{ and}$$

$$\omega(a\beta b) = \omega(a\beta b\beta a\beta b) \leq \omega(a\beta(b\beta a)\beta b) \leq \omega(b\beta a)$$

$$\omega(b\beta a) = \omega(b\beta a\beta b\beta a) \leq \omega(b\beta(a\beta b)\beta a) \leq \omega(a\beta b)$$

$$\text{Hence } \bar{\mu}(a\beta b) = \bar{\mu}(b\beta a) \text{ and } \omega(a\beta b) = \omega(b\beta a)$$

Therefore $\mathcal{A}(a\beta b) = \mathcal{A}(b\beta a)$.

Proposition 3.11: Let $\mathcal{A}_1 = \langle \bar{\mu}_1, \omega_1 \rangle$ be a cubic right ideal of S and $\mathcal{A}_2 = \langle \bar{\mu}_2, \omega_2 \rangle$ be a cubic left ideal of S , then $\mathcal{A}_1 \odot \mathcal{A}_2 \subseteq \mathcal{A}_1 \cap \mathcal{A}_2$.

Proof: Let $x \in S$. Suppose there exist $p, q \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$, such that $x \leq p\gamma q$. Then

$$(\bar{\mu}_1 \tilde{\circ} \bar{\mu}_2)(x) = \min_{x \leq p\gamma q} \{ \bar{\mu}_1(p), \bar{\mu}_2(q) \}$$

$$\leq \min_{x \leq p\gamma q} \{ \bar{\mu}_1(p\gamma q), \bar{\mu}_2(p\gamma q) \}$$

$$\leq \min\{ \bar{\mu}_1(x), \bar{\mu}_2(x) \}$$

$(\bar{\mu}_1 \tilde{\circ} \bar{\mu}_2)(x) \leq (\bar{\mu}_1 \cap \bar{\mu}_2)(x)$, suppose x cannot be expressed as $x \leq p\gamma q$, then

$(\bar{\mu}_1 \tilde{\circ} \bar{\mu}_2)(x) = \bar{0} \leq (\bar{\mu}_1 \cap \bar{\mu}_2)(x)$, this implies that $(\bar{\mu}_1 \tilde{\circ} \bar{\mu}_2)(x) \leq (\bar{\mu}_1 \cap \bar{\mu}_2)(x)$ and

$$(\omega_1 \circ \omega_2)(x) = \max_{x \leq p\gamma q} \{ \omega_1(p), \omega_2(q) \}$$

$$\geq \max_{x \leq p\gamma q} \{ \omega_1(p\gamma q), \omega_2(p\gamma q) \}$$

$$\geq \max\{ \omega_1(x), \omega_2(x) \}$$

$(\omega_1 \circ \omega_2)(x) \geq (\omega_1 \cup \omega_2)(x)$, suppose x cannot be expressed as $x \leq p\gamma q$, then

$(\omega_1 \circ \omega_2)(x) = 1 \geq (\omega_1 \cup \omega_2)(x)$, this implies that $(\omega_1 \circ \omega_2)(x) \geq (\omega_1 \cup \omega_2)(x)$

Hence $\mathcal{A}_1 \odot \mathcal{A}_2 \subseteq \mathcal{A}_1 \cap \mathcal{A}_2$.

Proposition 3.12: Let S be a regular Γ -semigroup, let $\mathcal{A}_1 = \langle \bar{\mu}_1, \omega_1 \rangle$ be a cubic right ideal of S and $\mathcal{A}_2 = \langle \bar{\mu}_2, \omega_2 \rangle$ be a cubic left ideal of S , then

$$\mathcal{A}_1 \odot \mathcal{A}_2 \supseteq \mathcal{A}_1 \cap \mathcal{A}_2.$$

Proof: Let $x \in S$. Since S is regular Γ -semigroup, then there exist $p \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$, such that $x = x\alpha p\beta x = x\gamma x$, where $\gamma = \alpha p\beta \in \Gamma$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\bar{\mu}_1 \tilde{\circ} \bar{\mu}_2)(x) &= \sup_{x=p\gamma q} \min\{\bar{\mu}_1(p), \bar{\mu}_2(q)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\bar{\mu}_1(x), \bar{\mu}_2(x)\} \\ (\bar{\mu}_1 \tilde{\circ} \bar{\mu}_2)(x) &\geq (\bar{\mu}_1 \cap \bar{\mu}_2)(x) \text{ and} \\ (\omega_1 \circ \omega_2)(x) &= \inf_{x=p\gamma q} \max\{\omega_1(p), \omega_2(q)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\omega_1(x), \omega_2(x)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$(\omega_1 \circ \omega_2)(x) \leq (\omega_1 \cup \omega_2)(x)$$

$$\text{Hence } \mathcal{A}_1 \odot \mathcal{A}_2 \supseteq \mathcal{A}_1 \cap \mathcal{A}_2.$$

Lemma 3.13: If $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic subset of S , then the following are equivalent:

i) $\bar{\mu} \tilde{*} \bar{\mu} \leq \bar{\mu}$ and $\omega * \omega \geq \omega$

ii) $\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\}$ and $\omega(x\gamma y) \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\}, \forall x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$.

Proof: Let $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. i) \rightarrow ii)

$$\text{Consider } (\bar{\mu} \tilde{*} \bar{\mu})(x\gamma y) = \sup_{x\gamma y=a\gamma_1 b} \min\{\bar{\mu}(a), \bar{\mu}(b)\} \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\}$$

By (i), $\bar{\mu} \tilde{*} \bar{\mu} \leq \bar{\mu}$

$$\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq (\bar{\mu} * \bar{\mu})(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\}.$$

Hence $\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\}$ and

$$(\omega * \omega)(x\gamma y) = \inf_{x\gamma y=a\gamma_1 b} \max\{\omega(a), \omega(b)\} \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\}$$

By (i), $\omega * \omega \geq \omega$

$$\omega(x\gamma y) \leq (\omega * \omega)(x\gamma y) \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\}$$

Hence $\omega(x\gamma y) \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\}$.

$$\text{ii) } \rightarrow \text{i) Consider } (\bar{\mu} \tilde{*} \bar{\mu})(x) = \sup_{x=a\gamma_1 b} \min\{\bar{\mu}(a), \bar{\mu}(b)\} \leq \sup_{x=a\gamma_1 b} \bar{\mu}(a\gamma_1 b) \leq \bar{\mu}(x)$$

This implies that $\bar{\mu} \tilde{*} \bar{\mu} \leq \bar{\mu}$

If x cannot be expressed as $x = a\gamma_1 b$, then $(\bar{\mu} \tilde{*} \bar{\mu})(x) = [0,0] \leq \bar{\mu}(x)$ this implies that

$$(\bar{\mu} \tilde{*} \bar{\mu})(x) \leq \bar{\mu}(x).$$

Hence $\bar{\mu} \tilde{*} \bar{\mu} \leq \bar{\mu}$.

$$\text{and } (\omega * \omega)(x) = \inf_{x=a\gamma_1 b} \max\{\omega(a), \omega(b)\} \geq \inf_{x=a\gamma_1 b} \omega(a\gamma_1 b) \geq \omega(x)$$

Thus $\omega * \omega \geq \omega$

If x cannot be expressed as $x = a\gamma_1 b$, then $(\omega * \omega)(x) = 1 \geq \omega(x)$ this implies that

$$(\omega * \omega)(x) \geq \omega(x).$$

Hence $\omega * \omega \geq \omega$.

Therefore $\bar{\mu} \tilde{*} \bar{\mu} \leq \bar{\mu}$ and $\omega * \omega \geq \omega$.

Lemma 3.14: A cubic subset $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ of S is a cubic left (right) ideal of S if and only if i) $\bar{\mu} \tilde{*} \bar{\mu} \leq \bar{\mu}$ and $\omega * \omega \geq \omega$

ii) $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H} \tilde{*} \bar{\mu} \leq \bar{\mu}$ and $\omega_{\chi_H} * \omega \geq \omega$, where the characteristic cubic set of S is denoted by $\chi_H = \langle \bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}, \omega_{\chi_H} \rangle$ of H in S and H is a non-empty subset of S .

Proof: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic left ideal of S . i) follows by above lemma 3.13.

Let $x \in S$. Suppose $x = a\gamma b$ for $x, a, b \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$.

$$\begin{aligned} (\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H} \tilde{*} \bar{\mu})(x) &= \sup_{x=a\gamma b} \min\{\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(a), \bar{\mu}(b)\} \\ &= \sup_{x=a\gamma b} \min\{[1,1], \bar{\mu}(b)\} \\ &= \sup_{x=a\gamma b} \bar{\mu}(b) \\ &\leq \sup_{x=a\gamma b} \bar{\mu}(a\gamma b) \\ &\leq \bar{\mu}(x) \end{aligned}$$

This implies that $(\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H} \tilde{*} \bar{\mu})(x) \leq \bar{\mu}(x)$

If x is not expressible as $x = a\gamma b$, then $(\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H} \tilde{*} \bar{\mu})(x) = [0,0] \leq \bar{\mu}(x)$. Thus $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H} \tilde{*} \bar{\mu} \leq \bar{\mu}$ and

$$\begin{aligned} (\omega_{\chi_H} * \omega)(x) &= \inf_{x=a\gamma b} \max\{\omega_{\chi_H}(a), \omega(b)\} \\ &= \inf_{x=a\gamma b} \max\{0, \omega(b)\} \\ &= \inf_{x=a\gamma b} \omega(b) \\ &\geq \inf_{x=a\gamma b} \omega(a\gamma b) \\ &\geq \omega(x) \end{aligned}$$

This implies that $(\omega_{\chi_H} * \omega)(x) \geq \omega(x)$

If x is not expressible as $x = a\gamma b$, then $(\omega_{\chi_H} * \omega)(x) = 1 \geq \omega(x)$. Thus $\omega_{\chi_H} * \omega \geq \omega$.

Conversely, let us assume that (i) and (ii) holds, by (ii)

Let $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Then we have,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) &\geq (\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H} \tilde{*} \bar{\mu})(x\gamma y) \\ &= \sup_{x\gamma y=p\gamma_1 q} \min\{\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(p), \bar{\mu}(q)\} \\ &\geq \min\{\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\} \\ &= \min\{[1,1], \bar{\mu}(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \bar{\mu}(y)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \omega(x\gamma y) &\leq (\omega_{\chi_H} * \omega)(x\gamma y) \\ &= \inf_{x\gamma y=p\gamma_1 q} \max\{\omega_{\chi_H}(p), \omega(q)\} \\ &\leq \max\{\omega_{\chi_H}(x), \omega(y)\} \\ &= \max\{0, \omega(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\omega(x\gamma y) \leq \omega(y)$$

Hence $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic left (right) ideal of S .

Theorem 3.15: The intersection of any family of cubic bi-ideals of Γ -semigroup S is a cubic bi-ideal of Γ -semigroup S .

Proof: Let $\{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ be the family of cubic bi-ideals of S , let $x, y, z \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \Gamma$.

Let $\bar{\mu}(x) = \cap \bar{\mu}_i(x) = (\inf \bar{\mu}_i)(x) = \inf \bar{\mu}_i(x)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \omega(x) &= \cup \omega_i(x) = (\sup \omega_i)(x) = \sup \omega_i(x) \\ \bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) &= \inf \bar{\mu}_i(x\gamma y) \geq \inf\{\min\{\bar{\mu}_i(x), \bar{\mu}_i(y)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\inf \bar{\mu}_i(x), \inf \bar{\mu}_i(y)\} = \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\} \\ \omega(x\gamma y) &= \sup \omega_i(x\gamma y) \leq \sup\{\max\{\omega_i(x), \omega_i(y)\}\} \\ &= \max\{\sup \omega_i(x), \sup \omega_i(y)\} = \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

Thus $\cap_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i$ is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of S .

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Again } \bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) &= \cap \bar{\mu}_i(x\alpha y\beta z) = \inf \bar{\mu}_i(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \inf \min\{\bar{\mu}_i(x), \bar{\mu}_i(z)\} \\ &= \min\{\inf \bar{\mu}_i(x), \inf \bar{\mu}_i(z)\} \\ &= \min\{\cap \bar{\mu}_i(x), \cap \bar{\mu}_i(z)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) &\geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(z)\} \text{ and} \\ \omega(x\alpha y\beta z) &= \cup \omega_i(x\alpha y\beta z) = \sup \omega_i(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \sup \max\{\omega_i(x), \omega_i(z)\} \\ &= \max\{\sup \omega_i(x), \sup \omega_i(z)\} \\ &= \max\{\cup \omega_i(x), \cup \omega_i(z)\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\omega(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \max\{\omega_i(x), \omega_i(z)\}$$

Hence $\cap_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S .

Theorem 3.16: A cubic set $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S if and only if the level set $U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n) = \{x \in S \mid \bar{\mu}(x) \geq \tilde{t} \text{ and } \omega(x) \leq n\}$ is a bi-ideal of S , when it is non-empty.

Proof: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic bi-ideal of S . Then

$$\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\} \text{ and } \omega(x\gamma y) \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\}$$

Let $x, y \in U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$, then $\bar{\mu}(x) \geq \tilde{t}, \bar{\mu}(y) \geq \tilde{t}$ and $\omega(x) \leq n, \omega(y) \leq n$.

$$\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\} \geq \min\{\tilde{t}, \tilde{t}\} = \tilde{t}$$

$$\omega(x\gamma y) \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\} \leq \max\{n, n\} = n$$

Thus $(x\gamma y) \in U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$

Also, $\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \bar{\mu}(y)$ and $\omega(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \omega(y)$ Let $x, y, z \in U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$, then $\bar{\mu}(x) \geq \tilde{t}, \bar{\mu}(y) \geq \tilde{t}, \bar{\mu}(z) \geq \tilde{t}$ and $\omega(x) \leq n, \omega(y) \leq n, \omega(z) \leq n$.

$$\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(z)\} \geq \min\{\tilde{t}, \tilde{t}\} = \tilde{t} \text{ and}$$

$$\omega(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(z)\} \leq \max\{n, n\} = n$$

Thus $(x\alpha y\beta z) \in U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$

Hence $U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$ is a bi-ideal of S.

Conversely, suppose that $U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$ is a bi-ideal of S.

Define $\tilde{t} = \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\}$ and $n = \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\}$

Let $x, y \in U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$ then $x\gamma y \in U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$

$$\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \tilde{t} \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\} \text{ and } \omega(x\gamma y) \leq n \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\}$$

Thus $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of S.

Also, define $\tilde{t} = \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(z)\}$ and $n = \max\{\omega(x), \omega(z)\}$

Let $x, y, z \in U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$, then $x\alpha y\beta z \in U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$

$$\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \tilde{t} \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(z)\} \text{ and } \omega(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq n \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(z)\}$$

Hence $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S.

Theorem 3.17: Let H be a non-empty subset of S. Then H is a bi-ideal of S if and only if the characteristic cubic set $\chi_H = \langle \bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}, \omega_{\chi_H} \rangle$ of H in S is a cubic bi-ideal of S.

Proof: Let H be a bi-ideal of S. Let $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Suppose that

$$\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x\gamma y) < \min\{\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x), \bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(y)\} \text{ and}$$

$$\omega_{\chi_H}(x\gamma y) > \max\{\omega_{\chi_H}(x), \omega_{\chi_H}(y)\} \text{ for some } x, y \in S, \text{ and } \gamma \in \Gamma.$$

Then $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x\gamma y) = \bar{0}, \bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x) = \bar{1} = \bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(y)$ and $\omega_{\chi_H}(x\gamma y) = 1, \omega_{\chi_H}(x) = 0 = \omega_{\chi_H}(y)$.

This implies that $x, y \in H$. Since H is a Γ -subsemigroup of S then $x\gamma y \in H$.

Thus $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x\gamma y) = \bar{1}$ and $\omega_{\chi_H}(x\gamma y) = 0$, a contradiction.

Hence $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x), \bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(y)\}$ and $\omega_{\chi_H}(x\gamma y) \leq \max\{\omega_{\chi_H}(x), \omega_{\chi_H}(y)\}$

Again suppose that $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x\alpha y\beta z) < \min\{\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x), \bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(z)\}$ and

$$\omega_{\chi_H}(x\alpha y\beta z) > \max\{\omega_{\chi_H}(x), \omega_{\chi_H}(z)\} \text{ for some } x, y, z \in S \text{ and } \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \Gamma. \text{ Then}$$

$$\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x\alpha y\beta z) = \bar{0}, \bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x) = \bar{1} = \bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(z) \text{ and } \omega_{\chi_H}(x\alpha y\beta z) = 1, \omega_{\chi_H}(x) = 0 = \omega_{\chi_H}(z).$$

This implies that $x, z \in H$. Since H is a bi-ideal of S, then $x\alpha y\beta z \in H$.

Thus $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x\alpha y\beta z) = \bar{1}$ and $\omega_{\chi_H}(x\alpha y\beta z) = 0$, a contradiction.

Hence $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x), \bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(z)\}$ and $\omega_{\chi_H}(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \max\{\omega_{\chi_H}(x), \omega_{\chi_H}(z)\}$

Hence $\chi_H = \langle \bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}, \omega_{\chi_H} \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S.

Conversely, assume that $\chi_H = \langle \bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}, \omega_{\chi_H} \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S, for any subset H of S.

Let $x, y \in H$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$, then $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x) = \bar{1} = \bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(y)$ and $\omega_{\chi_H}(x) = 0 = \omega_{\chi_H}(y)$.

Since χ_H is a cubic bi-ideal of S, thus $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x), \bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(y)\} \geq \min\{\bar{1}, \bar{1}\} = \bar{1}$

$$\text{and } \omega_{\chi_H}(x\gamma y) \leq \max\{\omega_{\chi_H}(x), \omega_{\chi_H}(y)\} \leq \max\{0, 0\} = 0.$$

This implies that $x\gamma y \in H$, for all $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Hence H is a Γ -subsemigroup of S.

Let $x, y, z \in H$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$, then $\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x) = \bar{1} = \bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(z)$ and $\omega_{\chi_H}(x) = 0 = \omega_{\chi_H}(z)$.

Since χ_H is a cubic bi-ideal of S, thus

$$\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(x), \bar{\mu}_{\chi_H}(z)\} \geq \min\{\bar{1}, \bar{1}\} = \bar{1} \text{ and } \omega_{\chi_H}(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq$$

$$\max\{\omega_{\chi_H}(x), \omega_{\chi_H}(z)\} \leq \max\{0, 0\} = 0.$$

This implies that $x\alpha y\beta z \in H$, for all $x, y, z \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Hence H is a bi-ideal of S.

Theorem 3.18: Let H be a non-empty subset of S. If $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic set of S defined by

$$\mathcal{A}(x) = \begin{cases} \bar{\mu}(x) = \begin{cases} [p_1, p_2] & \text{if } x \in H \\ [q_1, q_2] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ \omega(x) = \begin{cases} 1 - p & \text{if } x \in H \\ 1 - q & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{cases}$$

for all $x \in S$, $[p_1, p_2], [q_1, q_2] \in D[0,1]$ and $p, q \in [0,1]$ with $[p_1, p_2] > [q_1, q_2]$ and $p > q$. Then H is a bi-ideal of S if and only if $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S .

Proof: Let $x, y \in H$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. From the hypothesis $x\gamma y \in H$.

Assume that H is a bi-ideal of S .

We consider four cases:

i) $x \in H$ and $y \in H$

ii) $x \in H$ and $y \notin H$

iii) $x \notin H$ and $y \in H$

iv) $x \notin H$ and $y \notin H$

Case (i) If $x \in H$ and $y \in H$ then $\bar{\mu}(x) = [p_1, p_2] = \bar{\mu}(y)$ and $\omega(x) = 1 - p = \omega(y)$.

Since H is a bi-ideal of S . $\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) = [p_1, p_2] = \min\{[p_1, p_2], [p_1, p_2]\} = \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\}$ and $\omega(x\gamma y) = 1 - p = \max\{1 - p, 1 - p\} = \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\}$.

Case (ii) If $x \in H$ and $y \notin H$. Then $\bar{\mu}(x) = [p_1, p_2]$, $\bar{\mu}(y) = [q_1, q_2]$ and $\omega(x) = 1 - p$, $\omega(y) = 1 - q$.

Clearly, $\min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\} = [q_1, q_2]$ and $\max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\} = 1 - q$.

Now $\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) = [p_1, p_2]$ or $[q_1, q_2]$ and $\omega(x\gamma y) = 1 - p$ or $1 - q$

if $x\gamma y \in H$ or $x\gamma y \notin H$. By assumption that $[p_1, p_2] > [q_1, q_2]$ and $p > q$, then $\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\}$ and $\omega(x\gamma y) \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\}$.

Similarly we can prove that Case (iii).

Case(iv) If $x \notin H$ and $y \notin H$. Then $\bar{\mu}(x) = [q_1, q_2] = \bar{\mu}(y)$ and $\omega(x) = 1 - q = \omega(y)$.

So, $\min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\} = [q_1, q_2] = \bar{\mu}(x\gamma y)$ and $\max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\} = 1 - q = \omega(x\gamma y)$.

Therefore $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of S .

Let $x, y, z \in H$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$. From the hypothesis $x\alpha y\beta z \in H$.

Case(i) If $x \in H$ and $z \in H$ then $\bar{\mu}(x) = [p_1, p_2] = \bar{\mu}(z)$ and $\omega(x) = 1 - p = \omega(z)$.

Since H is a bi-ideal of S . $\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) = [p_1, p_2] \geq \min\{[p_1, p_2], [p_1, p_2]\} \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(z)\}$ and $\omega(x\alpha y\beta z) = 1 - p \leq \max\{1 - p, 1 - p\} = \max\{\omega(x), \omega(z)\}$.

Case (ii) If $x \in H$ and $z \notin H$. Then $\bar{\mu}(x) = [p_1, p_2]$, $\bar{\mu}(z) = [q_1, q_2]$ and $\omega(x) = 1 - p$, $\omega(z) = 1 - q$.

Clearly, $\min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(z)\} = [q_1, q_2]$ and $\max\{\omega(x), \omega(z)\} = 1 - q$.

Now $\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) = [p_1, p_2]$ or $[q_1, q_2]$ and $\omega(x\gamma y) = 1 - p$ or $1 - q$,

if $x\alpha y\beta z \in H$ or $x\alpha y\beta z \notin H$. By assumption that $[p_1, p_2] > [q_1, q_2]$ and $p > q$, then $\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(z)\}$ and $\omega(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(z)\}$.

Similarly we can prove that Case (iii).

Case(iv) If $x \notin H$ and $z \notin H$. Then $\bar{\mu}(x) = [q_1, q_2] = \bar{\mu}(z)$ and $\omega(x) = 1 - q = \omega(z)$.

So, $\min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(z)\} = [q_1, q_2] = \bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z)$ and $\max\{\omega(x), \omega(z)\} = 1 - q = \omega(x\alpha y\beta z)$.

Therefore $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S .

Conversely, assume that $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S . Let $x, y \in H$, and $\gamma \in \Gamma$.

Such that $\bar{\mu}(x) = [p_1, p_2] = \bar{\mu}(y)$ and $\omega(x) = 1 - p = \omega(y)$.

By hypothesis $\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\} = [p_1, p_2]$ and

$$\omega(x\gamma y) \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\} = 1 - p.$$

So, $x\gamma y \in H$. Therefore H is a Γ -subsemigroup of S .

Again, let $x, y, z \in H$, and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$.

Such that $\bar{\mu}(x) = [p_1, p_2] = \bar{\mu}(z)$ and $\omega(x) = 1 - p = \omega(z)$.

Then $\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) = [p_1, p_2] \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(z)\}$ and $\omega(x\alpha y\beta z) = 1 - p \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(z)\}$.

So, $x\alpha y\beta z \in H$. Therefore H is a bi-ideal of S .

Theorem 3.19: If $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S , then $\mathcal{A}^c = \langle (\bar{\mu})^c, (\omega)^c \rangle$ is also a cubic bi-ideal of S .

Proof: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S and let $x, y \in S, \gamma \in \Gamma$, then

$$(\bar{\mu})^c(x\gamma y) = 1 - \bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \leq 1 - \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\} = \max\{1 - \bar{\mu}(x), 1 - \bar{\mu}(y)\}$$

$$(\bar{\mu})^c(x\gamma y) \leq \max\{(\bar{\mu})^c(x), (\bar{\mu})^c(y)\}$$

$$(\omega)^c(x\gamma y) = 1 - \omega(x\gamma y) \geq 1 - \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\} = \min\{1 - \omega(x), 1 - \omega(y)\},$$

$$(\omega)^c(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{(\omega)^c(x), (\omega)^c(y)\}$$

Thus $\mathcal{A}^c = \langle (\bar{\mu})^c, (\omega)^c \rangle$ is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of S , and

Let $x, y, z \in S$, and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$, then

$$(\bar{\mu})^c(x\alpha y\beta z) = 1 - \bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq 1 - \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(z)\} = \max\{1 - \bar{\mu}(x), 1 - \bar{\mu}(z)\}$$

$$(\bar{\mu})^c(x\alpha y\beta z) \leq \max\{(\bar{\mu})^c(x), (\bar{\mu})^c(z)\}$$

$$(\omega)^c(x\alpha y\beta z) = 1 - \omega(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq 1 - \max\{\omega(x), \omega(z)\} = \min\{1 - \omega(x), 1 - \omega(z)\},$$

$$(\omega)^c(x\alpha y\beta z) \geq \min\{(\omega)^c(x), (\omega)^c(z)\}$$

Hence $\mathcal{A}^c = \langle (\bar{\mu})^c, (\omega)^c \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of S .

Proposition 3.20: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic ideal of S , then \mathcal{A} is a cubic interior ideal of S .

Proof: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic ideal of S , $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Then,

$$\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \bar{\mu}(x) \text{ and } \bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \bar{\mu}(y) \text{ which implies that}$$

$$\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\}.$$

Again, we have

$$\omega(x\gamma y) \leq \omega(x) \text{ and } \omega(x\gamma y) \leq \omega(y) \text{ which implies that}$$

$$\omega(x\gamma y) \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\}.$$

Hence $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of S .

Now let $x, y, z \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$. Then,

$$\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) = \bar{\mu}(x\alpha(y\beta z)) \geq \bar{\mu}(y\beta z) \geq \bar{\mu}(y) \text{ and}$$

$$\omega(x\alpha y\beta z) = \omega(x\alpha(y\beta z)) \leq \omega(y\beta z) \leq \omega(y)$$

Thus $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of S .

Proposition 3.21: Let S be a regular Γ -semigroup and $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic interior ideal of S , then \mathcal{A} is a cubic ideal of S .

Proof: Let $x, y \in S$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Since S is regular, for any $x \in S$ there exist $a \in S$, such that $x = x\alpha a\beta x$.

$$\text{Then, } \bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) = \bar{\mu}(x\alpha a\beta x\gamma y) \geq \bar{\mu}(x) \text{ and}$$

$$\omega(x\gamma y) = \omega(x\alpha a\beta x\gamma y) \leq \omega(x)$$

So, $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic right ideal of S .

Similarly, we can prove that $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic left ideal of S .

Hence $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic ideal of S .

Remark 3.22: From the above two propositions it is clear that in regular Γ -semigroups the concept of cubic ideals and cubic interior ideals are coincide.

Theorem 3.23: If $\{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ is a family of cubic interior ideals of S , then $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i$ is a cubic interior ideal of S .

Proof: Let $\{\mathcal{A}_i\}_{i \in \Lambda}$ be the family of cubic interior ideals of S .

Let $x, y, z \in S$ and $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \Gamma$ and

$$\text{let } \bar{\mu}(x) = \bigcap \bar{\mu}_i(x) = (\inf \bar{\mu}_i)(x) = \inf \bar{\mu}_i(x)$$

$$\omega(x) = \bigcup \omega_i(x) = (\sup \omega_i)(x) = \sup \omega_i(x),$$

$$\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) = \inf \bar{\mu}_i(x\gamma y) \geq \inf\{\min\{\bar{\mu}_i(x), \bar{\mu}_i(y)\}\}$$

$$= \min\{\inf \bar{\mu}_i(x), \inf \bar{\mu}_i(y)\} = \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\}$$

$$\omega(x\gamma y) = \sup \omega_i(x\gamma y) \leq \sup\{\max\{\omega_i(x), \omega_i(y)\}\}$$

$$= \max\{\sup \omega_i(x), \sup \omega_i(y)\} = \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\}$$

Thus $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mathcal{A}_i$ is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of S .

Again, $\bar{\mu}(y) = \inf \bar{\mu}_i(y) \leq \inf \{ \bar{\mu}_i(x\alpha\gamma\beta z) \} = \bar{\mu}(x\alpha\gamma\beta z)$ and

$$\omega(y) = \sup \omega_i(y) \geq \sup \{ \omega_i(x\alpha\gamma\beta z) \} = \omega(x\alpha\gamma\beta z)$$

Hence $\cap_{i \in \lambda} \mathcal{A}_i$ is a cubic interior ideals of S.

Theorem 3.24: Let S be a Γ - semigroup then $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of S if and only if the level set $U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n) = \{x \in S | \bar{\mu}(x) \geq \tilde{t} \text{ and } \omega(x) \leq n\}$ is an interior ideal of S, when it is non-empty.

Proof: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic interior ideal of S. Then

i) $\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\},$

ii) $\omega(x\gamma y) \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\}$

Let $x, y \in U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$, then $\bar{\mu}(x) \geq \tilde{t}, \bar{\mu}(y) \geq \tilde{t}$ and $\omega(x) \leq n, \omega(y) \leq n.$

$$\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\} \geq \min\{\tilde{t}, \tilde{t}\} = \tilde{t}$$

$$\omega(x\gamma y) \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\} \leq \max\{n, n\} = n$$

Thus $(x\gamma y) \in U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$

Also, i) $\bar{\mu}(x\alpha\gamma\beta z) \geq \bar{\mu}(y),$

ii) $\omega(x\alpha\gamma\beta z) \leq \omega(y),$

Let $x, y, z \in U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$, then

$$\bar{\mu}(x) \geq \tilde{t}, \bar{\mu}(y) \geq \tilde{t}, \bar{\mu}(z) \geq \tilde{t} \text{ and } \omega(x) \leq n, \omega(y) \leq n, \omega(z) \leq n.$$

$$\bar{\mu}(x\alpha\gamma\beta z) \geq \bar{\mu}(y) \geq \tilde{t} \text{ and } \omega(x\alpha\gamma\beta z) \leq \omega(y) \leq n$$

Thus $(x\alpha\gamma\beta z) \in U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$

Hence $U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$ is an interior ideal of S.

Conversely, suppose that $U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$ is an interior ideal of S.

Define $\tilde{t} = \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\}$ and $n = \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\}.$

Let $x, y \in U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$ then $x\gamma y \in U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$

$$\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \geq \tilde{t} \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\} \text{ and } \omega(x\gamma y) \leq n \leq \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\}$$

Thus $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of S.

Also, define $\tilde{t} = \bar{\mu}(y)$ and $n = \omega(y)$

Let $x, y, z \in U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$, then $x\alpha\gamma\beta z \in U(\mathcal{A}; \tilde{t}, n)$

$$\bar{\mu}(x\alpha\gamma\beta z) \geq \tilde{t} \geq \bar{\mu}(y) \text{ and } \omega(x\alpha\gamma\beta z) \leq n \leq \omega(y)$$

Hence $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of S.

4. Homomorphism of Cubic Ideals of Γ - Semigroups:

Definition 4.1: [2] A mapping f from a Γ - semigroup P to another Γ - semigroup Q is called a homomorphism, if $f(x\gamma y) = f(x)\gamma f(y) \quad \forall x, y \in S \text{ and } \forall \gamma \in \Gamma.$

Definition 4.2: [7] Let P and Q be given classical sets. A mapping f: P→Q induces two mappings $C_f: C(P) \rightarrow C(Q), \mathcal{A}_1 \rightarrow C_f(\mathcal{A}_1)$ and $C_f^{-1}: C(Q) \rightarrow C(P), \mathcal{A}_2 \rightarrow C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}_2).$

Where the mapping C_f is called cubic transformation and C_f^{-1} is called inverse cubic transformation.

Definition 4.3: Let f be a mapping from a set P to Q and $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic set of P then the image of P $C_f(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f(\bar{\mu}), C_f(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic set of Q is defined by

$$C_f(\mathcal{A})(x') = \begin{cases} C_f(\bar{\mu})(x') = \begin{cases} \sup_{f(x)=x'} \bar{\mu}(x) & \text{if } x' \in Q \\ [0,0] & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ C_f(\omega)(x') = \begin{cases} \inf_{f(x)=x'} \omega(x) & \text{if } x' \in Q \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \end{cases}$$

and

Let f be a mapping from a set P to Q and $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ be a cubic set of Q then the pre image of Q $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic set of P is defined by

$$C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A})(x) = \begin{cases} C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x)) = \bar{\mu}(f(x)) \\ C_f^{-1}(\omega(x)) = \omega(f(x)) \end{cases}$$

Theorem 4.4: Let $f: P \rightarrow Q$ be a homomorphism of Γ - semigroup S and let $C_f: C(P) \rightarrow C(Q)$ be the cubic transformation induced by f , if $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic bi- ideal of Q , then $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic bi- ideal of P .

Proof: Let $x, y \in P$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Then,

$$C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y)) = \bar{\mu}(f(x\gamma y)) = \bar{\mu}(f(x)\gamma f(y))$$

(since f is a homomorphism of Γ - semigroups)

$$C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y)) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(f(x)), \bar{\mu}(f(y))\} = \min\{C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu})(x), C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu})(y)\}$$

and

$$C_f^{-1}(\omega(x\gamma y)) = \omega(f(x\gamma y)) = \omega(f(x)\gamma f(y))$$

(since f is a homomorphism of Γ - semigroups)

$$C_f^{-1}(\omega(x\gamma y)) \leq \max\{\omega(f(x)), \omega(f(y))\} = \max\{C_f^{-1}(\omega)(x), C_f^{-1}(\omega)(y)\}$$

Therefore, $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of P .

Again, let $x, y, z \in P$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$. Then,

$$C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z)) = \bar{\mu}(f(x\alpha y\beta z)) = \bar{\mu}(f(x)\alpha f(y)\beta f(z)) \geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(f(x)), \bar{\mu}(f(z))\}$$

$$C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z)) \geq \min\{C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu})(x), C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu})(z)\}$$

and

$$C_f^{-1}(\omega(x\alpha y\beta z)) = \omega(f(x\alpha y\beta z)) = \omega(f(x)\alpha f(y)\beta f(z)) \leq \max\{\omega(f(x)), \omega(f(z))\}$$

$$C_f^{-1}(\omega(x\alpha y\beta z)) \leq \max\{C_f^{-1}(\omega)(x), C_f^{-1}(\omega)(z)\}$$

Hence, $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic bi-ideal of P .

Theorem 4.5: Let $f: P \rightarrow Q$ be a homomorphism of Γ - semigroup S and let $C_f: C(P) \rightarrow C(Q)$ be the cubic transformation induced by f ,

If $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of P , then $C_f(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f(\bar{\mu}), C_f(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of Q .

Proof: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of P , then it is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of P .

Let $x', y' \in Q$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$.

$$\begin{aligned} C_f(\bar{\mu})(x'\gamma y') &= \sup_{f(z)=x'\gamma y'} \bar{\mu}(z) \\ &\geq \sup_{f(x)=x', f(y)=y'} \bar{\mu}(x\gamma y) \\ &\geq \sup_{f(x)=x', f(y)=y'} \min\{\bar{\mu}(x), \bar{\mu}(y)\} \\ &= \min\{\sup_{f(x)=x'} \bar{\mu}(x), \sup_{f(y)=y'} \bar{\mu}(y)\} \\ &= \min\{C_f(\bar{\mu})(x'), C_f(\bar{\mu})(y')\} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} C_f(\omega)(x'\gamma y') &= \inf_{f(z)=x'\gamma y'} \omega(z) \\ &\leq \inf_{f(x)=x', f(y)=y'} \omega(x\gamma y) \\ &\leq \inf_{f(x)=x', f(y)=y'} \max\{\omega(x), \omega(y)\} \\ &= \max\{\inf_{f(x)=x'} \omega(x), \inf_{f(y)=y'} \omega(y)\} \\ &= \max\{C_f(\omega)(x'), C_f(\omega)(y')\} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $C_f(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f(\bar{\mu}), C_f(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of Q .

Again, let $x', y', z' \in Q$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} C_f(\bar{\mu})(x'\alpha y'\beta z') &= \sup_{f(z)=x'\alpha y'\beta z'} \bar{\mu}(z) \\ &\geq \sup_{f(x)=x', f(y)=y', f(z)=z'} \bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z) \\ &\geq \sup_{f(y)=y'} \bar{\mu}(y) \end{aligned}$$

$$C_f(\bar{\mu})(x'\alpha y'\beta z') \geq C_f(\bar{\mu})(y')$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} C_f(\omega)(x'\alpha y'\beta z') &= \inf_{f(z)=x'\alpha y'\beta z'} \omega(z) \\ &\leq \inf_{f(x)=x', f(y)=y', f(z)=z'} \omega(x\alpha y\beta z) \\ &\leq \inf_{f(y)=y'} \omega(y) \end{aligned}$$

$$C_f(\omega)(x'\alpha y'\beta z') \leq C_f(\omega)(y')$$

Hence $C_f(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f(\bar{\mu}), C_f(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of Q.

Theorem 4.6: Let $f: P \rightarrow Q$ be a homomorphism of Γ - semigroup S and let $C_f: C(P) \rightarrow C(Q)$ be the cubic transformation induced by f,

If $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of Q, then $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of P.

Proof: Let $\mathcal{A} = \langle \bar{\mu}, \omega \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of Q, then it is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of Q.

Let $x, y \in P$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y)) &= \bar{\mu}(f(x\gamma y)) = \bar{\mu}(f(x)\gamma f(y)) \\ &\geq \min\{\bar{\mu}(f(x)), \bar{\mu}(f(y))\} \end{aligned}$$

$$C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x\gamma y)) = \min\{C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu})(x), C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu})(y)\}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} C_f^{-1}(\omega(x\gamma y)) &= \omega(f(x\gamma y)) = \omega(f(x)\gamma f(y)) \\ &\leq \max\{\omega(f(x)), \omega(f(y))\} \end{aligned}$$

$$C_f^{-1}(\omega(x\gamma y)) = \max\{C_f^{-1}(\omega)(x), C_f^{-1}(\omega)(y)\}$$

Therefore, $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic Γ -subsemigroup of P.

Again, let $x, y, z \in P$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$. Then,

$$C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z)) = \bar{\mu}(f(x\alpha y\beta z)) = \bar{\mu}(f(x)\alpha f(y)\beta f(z)) \geq \bar{\mu}(f(y))$$

$$C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}(x\alpha y\beta z)) \geq C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu})(y)$$

and

$$C_f^{-1}(\omega(x\alpha y\beta z)) = \omega(f(x\alpha y\beta z)) = \omega(f(x)\alpha f(y)\beta f(z)) \leq \omega(f(y))$$

$$C_f^{-1}(\omega(x\alpha y\beta z)) \leq C_f^{-1}(\omega)(y)$$

Hence $C_f^{-1}(\mathcal{A}) = \langle C_f^{-1}(\bar{\mu}), C_f^{-1}(\omega) \rangle$ is a cubic interior ideal of P.

5. References:

1. K.T. Atanassov, "Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets", Fuzzy sets and systems, vol.20, no.1, pp.87-96, 1986.
2. V. Chinnadurai, "Fuzzy Ideals In Algebraic Structures", Lap lambert academic publishing, 2013.
3. V. Chinnadurai, K. Bharathivelan, S. Vijayabalaji and S. Sivaramakrishnan, "Cubic Ring", Global journal of pure and applied mathematics, vol.12, no.3, pp.947-950, 2016.
4. K. Hur and H.W. Kang, "Interval-Valued Fuzzy Subgroups And Rings", Honam math.jour., vol.32, pp.593-617, 2010.
5. Y.B. Jun, S.T. Jung and M.S. Kim, "Cubic Sub Algebras And Ideals Of BCK/BCI – Algebras", Far east journal of mathematical science vol.44, no.2, pp.239-250, 2010.
6. Y. B. Jun, S.T. Jung and M.S. Kim, "Cubic Subgroups", Annals of fuzzy mathematics and informatics, vol.2, no.1, pp.9 -15, 2011.
7. Y.B. Jun, C.S. Kim and K.O. Yang , "Cubic Sets", Annals of fuzzy mathematics and informatics, vol.4, no.1, pp.83-98, 2012.

8. Y.B. Jun and Asghar Khan, "Cubic Ideals In Semigroups", Honam mathematical journal, vol.35, no.4, pp.607-623, 2013.
9. Y.B. Jun, S.M. Hong and J. Meng, "Fuzzy Interior Ideals In Semigroups", Indian jour. of pure and app.math., vol.26, no.9, pp.859-863, 1995.
10. N. Kuroki, "On Fuzzy Ideals And Bi-ideals In Semigroups", Fuzzy sets and systems, vol.5, pp.203-205, 1981.
11. W.J. Liu, "Fuzzy Invariant Subgroups And Fuzzy Ideals", Fuzzy sets and systems vol.8, pp. 133-139, 1982.
12. D.R. Prince Williams, K.B. Latha and E. Chandrasekeran, "Fuzzy Bi- Γ -Ideals In Γ -Semigroups", Hacettepe journal of mathematics and statistics, vol.38, no.1, pp.9-15, 2009.
13. Sen M.K. and Saha N.K., "On Γ -Semigroup-I", Bull. calcutta math. soc. vol.3, pp.180-186, 1986.
14. S. Vijayabalaji and S. Sivaramakrishnan, "A Cubic Set Theoretical Approach To Linear Space", Abstract and applied analysis, vol. 2015, pp.1-8.
15. L. A. Zadeh, "Fuzzy Sets", Information and computation, vol.8, pp.338-353, 1965.
16. L. A. Zadeh, " The Concept of A Linguistic Variable And Its Applications To Approximate Reasoning I", Information sciences, vol.8, pp.199-249, 1975.